

CHARACTERISTICS OF QUANTITATIVE INDICATORS OF NEUROSONOGRAPHIC EXAMINATION OF NEWBORNS WITH PERINATAL CNS LESION

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Annotation: Relevance. Currently, perinatal lesions of the central nervous system of newborns occupy an important place in the structure of pathology of young children, which is associated with a high prevalence, severity of clinical manifestations and the risk of disability. Objective: to characterize the quantitative indicators of the neurosonographic study of newborns with perinatal central nervous system damage. Materials and methods: 120 newborns with moderate and severe perinatal central nervous system damage were examined: group I consisted of 40 newborns with moderate hypoxic perinatal central nervous system damage, group II included 40 newborns with severe hypoxic perinatal central nervous system damage. An increase in the size of the third and fourth ventricles, subarachnoid space, transparent septum cavity, cerebrospinal tract, pulsation of cerebral vessels, in group I up to $4,6\pm 0,2$, $5,1\pm 0,3$, $3,9\pm 0,2$, $4,6\pm 0,1$, $0,3\pm 0,2$, $0,1\pm 0,3$, $3,2\pm 2,3$, $6,1\pm 6,5$, $4,1\pm 2,3$, $3,1\pm 4,2$, $3,2\pm 3,1$ and $4,1\pm 3,5$ and in group II up to $5,9\pm 0,4$, $6,1\pm 0,5$, $9\pm 0,4$ ml. ml, $3,2\pm 0,2$, $0,1\pm 0,2$, $0,2\pm 0,1$, $2,5\pm 3,1$, $5,8\pm 6,0$, $4,6\pm 2,1$, $3,4\pm 4,1$, $3,1\pm 2,8$, $3,9\pm 3,1$ and $4,5\pm 3,2$ respectively.

Keywords: newborns, risk factors, perinatal encephalopathy, relative risk, reliability.

Relevance. Currently, perinatal lesions of the central nervous system of newborns occupy an important place in the structure of pathology of young children, which is associated with a high prevalence, severity of clinical manifestations and the risk of disability. The gas composition of the blood is the most objective parameters of the metabolic state of newborns. When identifying the features of the blood gas composition in newborns at birth, decompensated metabolic acidosis prevails in the main group ($p < 0.001$), which may be a prognostic criterion for the severity of the perinatal period.

Objective: to characterize the quantitative indicators of the neurosonographic study of newborns with perinatal central nervous system damage.

Materials and methods. 120 newborn babies were examined. The patients were divided into groups III: Group I consisted of 40 newborns with perinatal central nervous system damage of hypoxic genesis of moderate severity. Group II included 40 newborns with severe perinatal CNS damage of hypoxic origin. When diagnosing perinatal CNS lesions of hypoxic origin and determining the severity of the disease, ICD-10 was used.

The results of our research were entered into a database with subsequent statistical processing. Next, the analysis was carried out using the statistical software package "Statistica6.0" using a library of statistical functions with the calculation of the arithmetic mean (M), the error of the arithmetic mean (m), the Student's criterion (t). The value of $p < 0.05$ was accepted as the threshold level of statistical significance.

The results and their discussion. The analysis of childbirth revealed that all children with perinatal encephalopathy were born full-term with a gestational age of 38-42 weeks, body weight at birth ranged from 2800-4010 grams. There were 44 boys and 36 girls among the surveyed; 21 children aged 3-7 days, 59 9-28 days (Table 1).

Table 1 Distribution of sick children by gender and age in the examination groups

Examined	Amount	Gender		Age	
		Boys	Girls	3-7 days	8-28 days
Group I	40	20	20	8	32
Group II	40	16	24	13	27
Total	80	36	44	21	59

Of all patients, 13 (10.8%) were transferred from maternity hospitals within the third day from the onset of the disease, 63 (52.5%) – on 1-7 days and the remaining 44 (36.7%) – within 8-28 days.

The distribution of admitted patients by duration and severity of CNS lesion is shown in the table 2.

Table 2 Distribution of admitted patients by day and by severity of the disease

Severity degree	The number of newborns by degree	The number of newborns by days	
		3-7 days	8-28 days
Average	40	13	27
Severe	40	15	25
Total	80	28	52

An analysis of the distribution of patients by day of life and by severity of the disease shows that the admission of patients from maternity hospitals starting at 8 days is associated with the severity of central nervous system damage and the possibility of deterioration of transportation from another hospital, and as is known, strict rest is one of the fundamental principles of the treatment of newborns with brain damage in the first days of life, in this regard patients with severe central nervous system damage were much more likely to be admitted.

Image 1.

Distribution of examined sick children according to the duration of the disease at the time of admission

At the same time, it is obvious that patients with severe severity were admitted at an earlier date and only from maternity hospitals, due to the need for specialized medical care, including conducting a full comprehensive volume of research, and the need for specialized neurological and neurosurgical care.

The results of the main quantitative indicators of neurosonographic examination of the brain in newborns show changes characteristic of perinatal brain damage in all studied parameters (Table 3).

Table 3 Neurosonography data in newborns of the studied groups

№	Neurosonography data	Group I (n=40)	Group II (n=40)
1	Pathological changes	33-84%	41-100%
2	Swelling of the brain tissue	9-25%	26-63%
3	Increased echogenicity of periventricular zones	11-25%	23-56%
4	Periventricular leukomalacia	6- 17%	13-35%
5	Increased vascular pulsation	18-47%	-
6	Asymmetry of the ventricles	3-8%	5- 12%
7	PIVH Grade I (SEH)	10-25%	9-22%
8	PIVH Grade II	8- 20%	3-8%
9	PIVH Grade III	3-9%	6- 11%
10	PIVH Grade IV	1-2%	2-6%
11	Паренхиматозное кровоизлияние	2- 6%	-
12	Патологии не выявлено	6- 14%	-

Thus, there was an increase in the size of the third and fourth ventricles, subarachnoid space, transparent septum cavity, cerebrospinal tract, pulsation of cerebral vessels, in group I to $4,6 \pm 0,2$, $5,1 \pm 0,3$, $3,9 \pm 0,2$, $4,6 \pm 0,1$, $0,3 \pm 0,2$, $0,1 \pm 0,3$, $3,2 \pm 2,3$, $6,1 \pm 6,5$, $4,1 \pm 2,3$, $3,1 \pm 4,2$, $3,2 \pm 3,1$ and $4,1 \pm 3,5$ and in group II up to $5,9 \pm 0,4$, $6,1 \pm 0,5$, $9 \pm 0,4$ ml. ml, $3,2 \pm 0,2$, $0,1 \pm 0,2$, $0,2 \pm 0,1$, $2,5 \pm 3,1$, $5,8 \pm 6,0$, $4,6 \pm 2,1$, $3,4 \pm 4,1$, $3,1 \pm 2,8$, $3,9 \pm 3,1$ and $4,5 \pm 3,2$ respectively. The main instrumental indicators that objectively reflect the state of perinatal changes in the central nervous system are shown in Table 3.

Conclusions. Thus, the analysis of clinical syndromes and symptoms, as well as indicators of instrumental studies, shows that in newborns with perinatal central nervous system damage, they can further affect the child's health, and if untimely diagnosis can occur with a complicated and prolonged course of the disease of perinatal encephalopathy.

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